

1. Why is 16th edition of Dewey Decimal Classification called “Phoenix Schedule”?

Ans. The 16th edition of the Dewey Decimal Classification is often referred to as the "Phoenix Schedule" because it marked the first significant implementation of a revision method where outdated sections of the classification system were completely updated and replaced with new schedules, essentially "rising from the ashes" like a phoenix, signifying a major change while still maintaining the core structure of the Dewey Decimal Classification.

The two main features of this Edition are :

(i) This 16th edition of DDC was Published in two volumes-first volume containing the main schedules termed as **Tables** and second volume as **Relative Index**; (ii) The concept of **Phoenix Schedules** was introduced. This edition contained a completely new schedules for inorganic and organic chemistry 546-547.

● Key points :

I. Major change : This edition introduced the practice of completely revising specific subject areas within the DDC, discarding old classifications and introducing entirely new ones to better reflect current knowledge.

II. Gradual change : The "Phoenix Schedule" approach allows for substantial updates to the DDC without disrupting the entire system at once, enabling libraries to adapt to evolving knowledge gradually.

III. Symbolic meaning : The phoenix, a mythical bird that rises from its own ashes, represents the idea of renewal and transformation, perfectly aligning with the significant changes brought about by the 16th edition.

2. Why is Dewey Decimal Classification Index called Relative Index?

Ans. The Dewey Decimal Classification index is called a "relative index" because it shows how different aspects of a subject are related to each other across various disciplines, allowing users to find related topics even if they are classified in different sections of the system; essentially, it highlights the connections between subjects rather than just listing them in isolation.

It does not provide page numbers or direct references to the physical arrangement of the classification schedules. Instead, it helps users find the appropriate classification number for a given topic, regardless of its position within the DDC structure. This relative nature allows for flexibility and adaptability in classifying diverse subjects.

- **Key points :**

I. Subject connections : It lists subjects alphabetically, but also indicates which discipline or category each subject falls under within the Dewey Decimal Classification system.

II. Cross-referencing : If a topic is discussed in multiple disciplines, the relative index will point to the relevant Dewey Decimal numbers in each area.

III. Navigating complex topics : This feature helps users find information on a specific aspect of a broader subject by showing related concepts across different classifications.